

EDITORIAL: Interdisciplinary approach to corporate governance

Dear readers!

To date, future research trends will certainly concern sustainability and entrepreneurship due to the post-COVID-19 crisis.

Studies will focus on the determinants related to corporate governance, such as corporate ownership, which influence a person to undertake a business activity, or the role of institutional investors that can decide to invest in one nation rather than another, or a company that aims to get public by an IPO as a possible answer to the crisis. In this line of research, this issue welcomes the studies of *Marvin Nipper*, and *Hany El Beshlawy* and *Sinan Ardroumli*.

A future research trend will surely concern environmental and economic sustainability for several reasons. First, climate change will affect all countries in the world: therefore, all countries are in a position to act altogether or do not at all; otherwise the advantage of the free-rider will occur. Second, climate change can represent an obstacle to the development strategies of companies, forced to incur costs, such as research and development costs, to comply with new rules imposed by policy-makers. The quality of the internal controls of the companies, the responsibility of the directors, the truthfulness of the financial statements and the amount of non-financial information contained in the financial and non-financial reporting will play a fundamental role in academic studies. The studies of *Shivneil Kumar Raj* and *Mohammed Riaz Azam*, *Hugh Grove* and *Macllyn Clouse*, *Karim Hegazy* and *Anne Stafford*, *Hidaya Al Lawati* and *Khaled Hussainey* fit into this line of research. In this context, the authors of previous research have already established fundamental pillars to this issue of research (Sylos Labini, Kostyuk, & Govorun, 2020; Dell'Atti, Manzanegue, & Hundal, 2020; Maglio, Rey, Agliata, & Lombardi, 2020a; Megginson, de Andres, Brogi, & Govorun, 2019; Collin, 2008; Turnbull, 2005) and the authors of the papers published in this issue of the journal made these fundamentals more solid.

Another line of research will concern the protection of biodiversity and gender equality. Better gender equality in education and participation in the labor market and a more equitable sharing of unpaid care activities between women and men could be levers for creating value in the future. Empirical studies deal with the impact of external interventions by policymakers and internal managers to understand the relationship between biodiversity and the financial and non-financial performance of companies. This issue includes the study by *Rehab EmadEldeen*, *Ahmed F. Elbayoumi*, *Mohamed A. K. Basuony*, and *Ehab K. A. Mohamed*. Certainly, the gender issue spreads over many aspects of corporate governance and the most important and demanded by the researchers in the context of the board of directors (Morris, Sodjahnin, & Boubacar, 2021; Maglio, Rey, Agliata, & Lombardi, 2020b; Velte, 2017; Modiba & Ngwakwe, 2017; Gennari, 2016; Shehata, 2013; Torchia, Calabrò, Huse, & Brogi, 2010; Zelechowski & Bilimoria, 2006).

With the regard to the content of this issue, ownership structure is the most popular issue considered by the authors of the papers. Thus, one of the studies investigated the influence of ownership control on 222 public US companies' performance after the 2008 financial crisis. The authors identify a new construct representing a third dimension (control intensity) of ownership structure, whereas previous literature has identified only two dimensions: identity and concentration. The control intensity construct of managerial ownership was measured using the number of manager-owners among individual shareholders instead of using the traditional ownership concentration

measurement method. Another study aimed to examine the impact of foreign ownership on the performance of Indian firms. Additionally, it also analyses the non-linear relationship of foreign ownership with firm performance. The papers published in this issue of the journal contributed to the previous research by Kostyuk, Tutino, and Prigge (2019), Kostyuk, Braendle, and Capizzi (2017), Habbash (2015), Arouri, Hossain, and Muttakin (2011), Rogers, Dami, de Sousa Ribeiro, and de Sousa (2008), Chapelle (2004).

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